

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row.
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

IR64 compared with recently released ASD16 and other IR varieties

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IR64 was compared with recently released TNAU variety ASD16 and IR50, IR60, and IR62 in a Summer 1986 trial. The random block replicated trial

Table 2. Resistance^a of ASD16 and 4 IR varieties to pests and diseases at Coimbatore, India, 1986 summer.

Variety	Reaction to insects				Reaction to diseases	
	BPH	GLH	WBPH	BB	B1	RTV
IR50	S	S	S	S	S	MR
IR60	S	MR	S	S	R	R
IR62	R	R	R	R	RR	
IR64	R	R	R	R	RR	
ASD16	S	S	S	MR	MR	S

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

Table 1. Performance of ASD16 and 4 IR varieties at Coimbatore, India, 1986 summer.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers/plant	Grains/panicle	Empty grains/panicle	Grain yield (g/plant)	Straw yield (g/plant)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
IR50	110	69.5	10	111	23	12.4	9.1	21.2	4.6
IR60	115	72.8	11	108	20	11.7	8.9	21.3	4.8
IR62	125	82.1	9	110	20	15.3	13.6	23.9	4.6
IR64	120	83.1	11	118	16	18.2	12.9	26.9	5.0
ASD16	115	97.2	8	102	19	16.7	15.4	24.2	4.8
CD		3.5	2.2	9.5	—	3.4	—	1.5	—

was planted 3 Apr and harvested on 6 Oct. At harvest, 10 plants from each replication were assessed for yield and yield-contributing characters. IR64 yielded 5.0 t/ha, 0.2 t/ha more than ASD16 and IR60 (Table 1). IR64 and IR62 compare in height, but IR62 takes 5 d longer to mature. The grain of

IR64 is long slender.

IR64 is resistant to brown planthopper (BPH), green leafhopper (GLH), and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) and moderately resistant to blast (B1), bacterial blight (BB), and tungro (RTV) (Table 2). □

A simplified method to classify rice varieties with isozymes

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Analyses of isozyme variation at 15 to 21 loci among traditional *O. sativa* rices from all continents have led to the identification of 6 varietal groups: indica (group I); japonica, with its temperate

and tropical forms (group VI), and 4 marginal groups restricted to the north of the Indian subcontinent (groups II to V). The method used to determine the classification of a given variety involves at least 15 loci and requires electrophoretic survey of at least 10 enzymes.

We have developed a simplified procedure based on five diagnostic genes which permit classifying most varieties. These genes are *Pgi-1* and *Pgi-2*, which encode phosphoglucose isomerases, and *Amp-3*, *Amp-2*, and *Amp-1*, which

A simple method to classify rice varieties with isozymes, using their genotypes at the 5 loci *Pgi-1*, *Pgi-2*, *Amp-3*, *Amp-2*, and *Amp-1*. IRRI, 1987.

encode aminopeptidases efficient with leucyl- β -naphthylamide, alanyl- β -naphthylamide, and both substrates. The enzymes are extracted by grinding a single plumule in a few drops of water and are separated by 4 h electrophoresis at 15 V/cm in a 14% starch gel, with a

Tris (0.009M)-Histidine (0.005M) gel buffer, pH 8.0, and a Tris (0.400M)-Citrate (0.105M) electrode buffer, pH 8.0. They are stained using standard procedures.

The resulting zymograms are translated in terms of loci and alleles.

These data are used to assign a given variety to one of the groups. An algorithm with five steps, corresponding to the five loci, where the criteria taken into consideration are the alleles of the variety at these loci, is used (see figure).

The original and the simplified

methods were compared using a sample of more than 3,000 traditional varieties. The classification coincided in 99% of the cases. In the other 1%, rices fell into one group in one case and were

classified intermediaries in the other case.

A similar finding was observed among modern varieties produced by hybridization within a group. Of 87 varieties whose parentage involves at

least 2 different groups, only 4 (5%) gave different results using the 2 methods.

The simplified method is highly reliable. It is fast, cheap, and requires no sophisticated equipment. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Ratooning ability of IR varieties in Hangzhou, China

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We evaluated 28 IR varieties, from IR5 to IR64, for ratooning ability. Pregerminated seeds were sown on 18 Apr 1986 in a screenhouse and 8 plants of each variety were transplanted on 17 May at 20- × 15-cm spacing. At maturity, plants were cut to 15-cm height and scored for ratooning ability 15 d after cutting.

IR29, IR30, IR43, and IR64 had relatively high ratooning ability; ratoon crops yielded about 50% of main crops (see table). In 13 varieties, ratooning was intermediate; ratoon crops yielded 20-30% of main crops. In seven varieties, the ratoon crops did not head because of the long growth duration of the main crop and subsequent low temperatures during the ratoon crop. Main crop and ratoon crop growth durations and yields did not correlate. □

Average duration and grain yield of IR varieties in main crop and ratoon crop. Hangzhou, China, 1986.

Variety	Main crop		Ratoon crop		Ratoon scale
	Maturity (d)	Yield (g/plant)	Maturity (d)	Yield (g/plant)	
IR5	171	14.9	—	—	—
IR8	167	15.7	—	—	—
IR20	164	14.6	—	—	—
IR22	145	14.5	48	4.2	5
IR24	123	16.5	56	4.5	5
IR26	126	13.1	46	3.8	5
IR28	111	16.2	52	1.8	9
IR29	118	11.7	47	5.8	1
IR30	119	12.4	50	6.4	1
IR32	172	14.4	—	—	—
IR34	148	16.3	44	3.8	5
IR36	120	15.7	48	4.1	5
IR38	134	12.6	50	2.4	5
IR40	155	12.8	—	—	—
IR42	164	11.7	—	—	—
IR43	135	12.3	42	6.0	1
IR44	131	11.4	49	2.7	5
IR45	141	11.9	51	3.3	5
IR46	151	13.0	41	2.6	5
IR48	167	11.6	—	—	—
IR50	114	11.9	50	1.5	9
IR52	130	11.6	54	2.9	5
IR54	133	13.0	57	3.0	5
IR56	119	14.8	43	2.9	5
IR58	110	12.1	42	1.7	9
IR60	120	12.9	41	1.4	9
IR62	143	13.8	45	2.6	5
IR64	126	12.5	51	6.1	1

Performance of CR666 rice cultures

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To identify a very short-duration variety that can fit into the 60-d fallow between 2 turmeric crops in Kalingarayan canal tract, we tested 5 promising lines of CR666. The entries were direct seeded on 16 Jul 86 in a randomized block design replicated three times. Because no local variety is in the 60-d duration

Performance of CR666 lines at Coimbatore, India, 1986.

Line	Duration (d)	Mean plant ht (cm)	Mean tillers/plant	Panicle length (cm)	Yield (t/ha)
CR666-14	75	68	6	17	1.3
CR666-18	74	71	8	17	1.9
CR666-36-4	75	66	6	16	0.8
CR666-37-38	73	87	6	21	1.5
CR666-119	75	65	7	17	0.9

group, a local check could not be included.

The 5 lines, which reportedly mature in 60 d at Cuttack, took about 15 d longer at Coimbatore, perhaps because

of the difference in latitude and elevation. Cuttack is situated 20° 30'N at 23 m, Coimbatore at 11° 02'N at 431 m. CR666-18 gave the maximum yield, followed by CR666-37-38 (see table). □